

Poll: Religious Place (v1.2)

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Zaouia Sidi Abi Sa'id al-Baji زاوية أبي سعيد الباجي

By Bou Ali Malika, Zaytouna

Entry tags: Sufi, Religious Group, Tunisia, North Africa, Religious Place, Islamic Traditions, Mysticism, Sufi Order

هي زاوية في منطقة سيدي بو سعيد التي أخذت اسمها من وجود مقام الولي الصالح أبي سعيد الباجي فيها. هو مقام وضرخ يتبرك به عاقبة الناس ويكثر تسمية الأبناء باسم هذا الولي

Date Range: 1156 CE - 2022 CE

Region: La Marsa Sidi Bou Sa'id al-Baji

Region tags: Africa, Northern Africa, Tunisia, North Africa, Tunisia

C'est au nord de la capital Tunis

Status of Participants:

 Elite Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: أبو الحسن علي بن أبي القاسم الهواري، مناقب أبي سعيد الباجي، الشركة التونسية للنشر وتوزيع فنون الرسم، تونس، 2004.
 - Source 2: 1965. محمد البهلي النبال؛ الحقيقة للتصويف الإسلامي، طبعة أولى، تونس.
 - Source 3: 1988. براشفيك روبا، تاريخ إفريقيّة في العهد الحفصي، ترجمة حمادي السالح، تونس.
- Reference: سلامة العامري، تلي. الولاية والمجتمع الولاية والمجتمع مساهمة في التاريخ الاجتماعي والديني الإفريقيّة في 2006. العهد الحفصي، بيروت: دار الفرابي.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://observers.france24.com/ar/20130115-%D8%A5%D8%AD%D8%B1%D8%A7%D9%82-%D8%B6%D8%B1%D9%8A%D8%AD-%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D9%8A-%D8%A8%D9%88%D8%B3%D8%B9%D9%8A%D8%AF-%D8%A3%D8%AD%D8%B1%D9%82%D8%AA-%D9%85%D8%B5%D8%A7%D8%AD%D9%81-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%82%D8%B1%D8%A2%D9%86-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AA%D9%8A-%D8%AE%D8%B7%D9%87%D8%A7-%D8%A3%D9%82%D8%B1%D8%A8-%D8%AA%D9%84%D8%A7%D9%85%D9%8A%D8%B0-%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%88%D9%84%D9%8A-%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%B5%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%AD-%D8%AA%D9%88%D9%86%D8%B3>
- Source 1 Description: Une histoire de la diffamation de la Zaouia
- Source 1 URL: https://www.google.com/search?q=%D9%85%D9%82%D8%A7%D9%85+%D8%B3%D9%8A%D8%AF%D9%8A+%D8%A3%D8%A8%D9%8A+%D8%B3%D8%B9%D9%8A%D8%AF&rl38AWxRFEDHcE2BqoQ_AUoAnoECAEQBA&biw=1280&bih=601&dpr=1.5#fpstate=ive&vld=cid:74fbd0c3,vid:LAWIio4BE5U
- Source 1 Description: يصف البرنامج تاريخ بناء المقام والإضافات التي حصلت خاصة بعد حرقه في 2013 والإكتشافات الحفريّة الجديدة حيث وجدت أعمدة تعود للفترة الرومانيّة ق 3 ق م وأعمدة أخرى تعود للفترة الحفصيّة في ق 13 كما اكتشفت مقبرة والآن المعهد الوطني للتراث يبحث عن هويّة الموتى وقد يتغير ذلك قراءة التاريخ سيدي بوسعيد
- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2MSe4GHubOk&ab_channel=66KIF
- Source 1 Description: رحلة مهمة للمنزلة سيدي بوسعيد وحقائق الإكتشافات الجديدة للأعمدة وكرسي الصلّح المعروف في المنطقة

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

— No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

—Elevation

Type of elevation
—Hill

– Mountain

– Other [specify]: دفن سيدي أبي سعيد (1156م _ 1230 م) في منطقة " جبل منارة " قرطاج وحمل المكان اسمه في صاحبة سيدي بوسعيد

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:
– No

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:
Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?
– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure
– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Rectangular

↳ One single feature
– Other [specify]: كان أبي سعيد الباجي مقيما بجبل " المنارة " ويسمى جبل " المرسي ويجمع تلامذته في حلقة الذكر

↳ A group of structures:
– No

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal

- ↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
 - Yes
- ↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
 - Yes
 - Notes: كان المقام عبارة على مسجد صغير تمّ وقع توسعته وبعد وفاة الشيخ ابوسعيد وضع الصريح داخله وفي 2011 وقع حرق المقام من الأريانيين فوق تجديده وإعادة ترميمه
- ↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed
 - Other [specify]: وقع تدميره في 2012 من قبل السلفيين
 - ↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:
 - For religious reasons
 - As the result of pillage
 - ↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:
 - Human-caused accident
- ↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
 - Yes
 - ↳ In antiquity
 - More than once
 - ↳ In modernity
 - Post-Renaissance
 - Notes: بعد احراق المقام وقعت أشغال كبيرة للإعادة ترميم الأسس وساهمت أطراف كثيرة كوكالة الوطنية لحماية التراث و المعهد الوطني للتراث و البلدية إلى جانب مساعدات مادّية تلقاها للأهالي شاهد https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AwQpuMjjjdg&list=RDCMUC-48PCT3fIS86JKLzxiTA9g&ab_channel=NessmaTV

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

- ↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
 - Yes [specify]: أوّجّد أنّ العبادة تتجّه لله الواحد ولكنّ الناس يتبرّكون بالولي الضالّح سيدي بوسعيد لما عرف به من تقوى وعلم وبرى عنه أنّه إذ كان في ميعاد الذكر تتباه نوبات من الإغماء

- ↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
 - No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:
A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.
– Yes

- ↳ Specify

- King or emperor
- Religious specialists affiliated with political entity
- Private individual

– Other [specify]: قام الباي حسين باي ببناء الجامع في القرن 18 لكن بعد حرق المقام واعادة الترميم وقعت حفريات اكتشفت على إثرها وجود أعمدة تعود للفترة الرومانية ق 3_ 4 ق م و أعمدة أخرى تعود للفترة الحفصية في ق 13 كما اكتشفت مقبرة والآن المعهد الوطني للتراث يبحث عن هويّة الموتى وقد يغيّر ذلك قراءة التاريخ سيدي بوسعيد

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

Groups:

- Corvee labourers
- Men
- Women
- Specialized labourers/craftspeople

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: أراد الباي استرضاء أبي سعيد الباجي ف ساعد في بتوسيعه بعد أن كان محوّذ خلوة وساحة

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: الذين يزورون الراوية يكونون من الناس العاديين لطلب بركة الوليسيدي بوسعيد في زيادة الرزق أو الشفاء أو إيجاب الأبناء كما يزوره بعض المثقفين من السياسيين والفنانين والتجار والأغنياء

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: يفتح المقام والجامع على مقبرة قديمة نصل إليها عبر مدّح يعرف ب"كرسي الصلّاح" فيها 360 درجة كلّ درجة مدفون فيها أحد الصّالحين

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: site plurielle : https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2MSe4CHubOk&ab_channel=66KIF

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– Percentage: 30

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

Notes: توجد بالجامع أشهر صومعة بهندستها المعماريّة التقليديّة وهي صومعة كبيرة وعالية يصعد إليها بمرح ضيق. يصل عرضه 54 متر ويرتفع لـ 8 طوابق تشرف على 5 ولايات وهي تونس منوبة أريانة بنعروس نابل

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Sand
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Wood
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Grass
 - No
- ↳ Stone
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material sourced locally:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
 - No
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: Il y a des portes en bois, des décorations en fer pour les fenêtres, des mosaïques et des décorations murales blanches

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

- Yes [specify]: Portes en bois, décorations gravées en fer pour les fenêtres, mosaïques, décorations vertes et rouges pour les colonnes... Quant à la façade du sanctuaire, avant d'être brûlée, elle portait des décorations manuscrites.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

- Yes

- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
 - Yes

- ↳ On the outside:
 - Yes

- ↳ On the inside:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
 - Yes

- ↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

 - Yes

- ↳ Are there gods depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there humans depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there animals depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - No
 - Notes: Bien que toutes les réponses soient non, il faut souligner qu'il y a une forte présence de ce qui est divin et surnaturel dans le lieu, comme les tableaux et les décorations dans lesquelles se trouvent des versets coraniques ou des poèmes prononcés par le cheikh dans son "mystique". chemin" ou en louant le Saint Prophète comme le poème d'Al-Basiri à la louange de L'apôtre décoré sur le périmètre en bois du cercueil à côté du sanctuaire, qui n'a pas été brûlé site plurielle : https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2MSe4GHubOk&ab_channel=66KIF
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: استعمال كتابات مقدّسة
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - No
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there reliefs present:
 - A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.
 - No
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they wall paintings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Type
 - Secco

- ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - No
- ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - No
- ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - Yes
 - Notes: بعد الحرق اكتشف كتابات من أبيات " البردة " على أحد الأضرحة
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: استعمال لألوان كثيرة للزينة خاصة الأحمر والأخضر والأبيض والأزرق
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - No
 - ↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
 - No
 - ↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:
 - No
 - ↳ Abstract mosaics:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Le mélange des couleurs peut être important avec l'intensité du vert
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Il contient des versets coraniques
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - No
- Yes
- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
 - Yes
 - ↳ On the outside:
 - Yes

- ↳ On the inside:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries
 - Yes
- ↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

 - Yes
 - ↳ Are there gods depicted:
 - No
 - ↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:
 - No
 - ↳ Are there humans depicted:
 - No
 - ↳ Are there animals depicted:
 - No
 - ↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:
 - No
- ↳ Is the decoration non-figural:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it geometric/abstract
 - Yes
 - ↳ Floral motifs
 - Yes
 - ↳ Is it writing/caligraphy
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: بعد حرق المقام وقع اكتشاف أعمدة وزخارف رومانية وأخرى تعود للفترة الحفصية ووقع إصافتها للمقام
- ↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:
 - No
- ↳ Are there statues present:
 - No
- ↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

 - No
- ↳ Are there paintings present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

- Yes
- ↳ Are they wall paintings:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Type
 - Secco
 - ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - No
 - ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - No
 - ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: Il y a aussi des écrits, y compris des versets coraniques et des versets poétiques qui louent le Messager
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - No
 - ↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
 - No
 - ↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:
 - No
 - ↳ Abstract mosaics:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: حتى بعد حرق المقام وقع إعادة استعمال الموزاييك على الواجهة الأمامية للمقام
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - No
 - ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: النقوش ليست كثيرة مقارنة بالمقامات الأخرى فهي بسيطة على شاكلة الهندسة المعمارية التقليدية
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - No

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: تعتبر الزخرفة بسيطة لاختلاف عن الطابع المعماري لمدينة سيدي بوسعيد

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–Secco

- ↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:
 - No
- ↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:
 - No
- ↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: كثافة استعمال اللونين الأخضر والحمر وله دلالات رمزيّة عند الطوّقيّة
- ↳ Are there mosaics present:
 - Yes
- ↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:
 - No
- ↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:
 - No
- ↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:
 - No
- ↳ Abstract mosaics:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: هندسة المقام بسيطة
- ↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]:
 - Yes
- ↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:
 - No
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: non
- ↳ Other type of decoration:
 - Yes [specify]: المقام بسيط في هندسته المعماريّة
- Yes
- ↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):
 - Yes
- ↳ On the outside:
 - Yes
- ↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– No

Notes: ليس هناك عبادة لأشخاص ولذلك يتبرك الناس بالصريح الرمزي رغم معرفتهم بأن الشيخ ليس مدفونا فيه

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– No

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: توجد كثير من الكتابات على اللوحات منها آيات قرآنية أو أبيات شعرية قالها الشيخ في مدح الرسول ومدح " طريفته الطوفية ". كما توجد نقوش زخرفية في الواجهة الأمامية للمقام ورسوم بها بيت شعري من قصيدة البصري في مدح الرسول على السياج الخشبي المحيط بأحد الأضرحة

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: وقعت العناية بالمقام بعد حرقه فأضيف له الأعمدة الرومانية التي وقع اكتشافها وأصبحت ظاهرة للناس بجانب المقام كما وقع استعمال الحجارة الصخرية في عملية الترميم والحليز التقليدي الذي كان يستعمل داخل المنازل القديمة بسيدي بوسعيد

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

Notes: Les peintures ne sont pas des photos de personnes ou de paysages, mais des écrits sacrés de versets coraniques ou des beaux noms de Dieu " Asmaa Allah Alhousna ", ou des paroles tirées de ce qu'a dit le cheikh Abu Said.

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

Notes: Il est possible d'écrire des vers poétiques que le cheikh a dit sur les panneaux, et une nouvelle écriture a été découverte dans de nombreuses couleurs contenant un verset poétique du purdah à la louange du Messager après l'incendie du sanctuaire et il a été trouvé dans une pièce connue comme la retraite " Elkhoulou " dans laquelle Abu Saeed réside dans un cercle pour le "dthikre " après avoir enlevé le cadre en bois qui entourait l'un des sanctuaires

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: site plurielle : https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2MSe4GHubOk&ab_channel=66KIF

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Mosaïque abstraite à l'intérieur du maqam

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative
[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Il faut faire attention aux usages symboliques des couleurs dans le sanctuaire de Sidi Bou Saïd, car la couleur verte est majoritairement utilisée, qui symbolise la verdure, la fertilité et le paradis. Et la couleur rouge, qui symbolise la connaissance chez les soufis et est un nom pour le soufre rouge selon le mystique musulman Ibn Arabi, en plus de la couleur blanche, symbolisant la pureté et la pureté de l'âme, et la couleur bleue comme le ciel et la mer, qui symbolise le soufisme pour le chemin de la connaissance

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: يوجد فوق الأعمدة أفواس نصف دائرية مزينة بخطوط بيضاء وسوداء وهي أيضا من الفن المعماري في الهندسة التقليدية

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– No

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: كرسي الصلاة

Notes: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2MSe4GHubOk&ab_channel=66KIF

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ Are they sky deity:

– No

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– No

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Yes

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Les musulmans croient en un seul Dieu et non en plusieurs dieux

Notes: C'est le lien d'obéissance au cheikh, qui était connu pour son ascèse et son soutien aux opprimés et aux pauvres. Il est intervenu pour libérer les prisonniers et a gardé son phare avec les soldats sur la côte tunisienne pendant les croisades. C'est pourquoi il était appelé le "Raiis Abhar".

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: بعض الناس من المريرين أثناء حلقة الذكر وقراءة اوراد الشيخ "كحزب اللطيف" و"حزب البحر" قد يتمكّنون من رؤية الشيخ او كائنات اخرى كالملائكة كما يروي عن الشيخ أنه عندما كان مريضا دخلت عليه الملائكة والجنّ فسلم عليهم أبو سعيد وهو يقول " هنا يا ملائكة الله ، هنا يا وفد الله

↳ Nonhuman spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Yes

Notes:

[http://www.mawsouaa.tn/wiki/%D9%85%D8%B9%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A3%D9%88%D9%84%D9%8A%D8%A7%\[](http://www.mawsouaa.tn/wiki/%D9%85%D8%B9%D8%A7%D9%84%D9%85_%D8%A7%D9%84%D8%A3%D9%88%D9%84%D9%8A%D8%A7%[)

↳ Supernatural monitoring of norm adherence:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect offerings:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Notes: Parfois, les gens demandent de l'aide pour des problèmes sexuels ou demandent à avoir des enfants

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect proper ritual observance:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect performance of rituals:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect maintenance of the place:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about or expect personal hygiene:

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about honoring oaths:

– No

↳ Other:

–Other [specify]: Les pouvoirs surnaturels n'interfèrent pas directement, mais les gens recherchent les bénédictions de l'esprit du cheikh ou des anges, demandant de l'aide, de la nourriture, de la guérison ou facilitant le mariage et ayant des enfants.

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Do visitors communicate with gods:

– No

↳ Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: Certaines personnes peuvent s'adresser au monde, et on savait que le cheikh Abu Saeed Al-Baji communiquait avec les anges et les djinns pendant sa maladie et les saluait en disant Hnaya, les anges de Dieu, Hnaya wafd Allah.

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: 2000

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: 40

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: هناك حلقات من الذكر لآيات قرآنية أو قراءة أوراد الشيخ كحرب اللطيف وحزب البحر أو أناشيد تمجّد سيرة أبي سعيد الباجي

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Les offres matérielles sont variées et non inclusives

Notes: Les cadeaux et les dons peuvent avoir une valeur, comme de l'argent, de la nourriture, des couvertures, des meubles et des sacrifices. Le cheikh avait l'habitude de les distribuer aux pauvres, et il a été rapporté de lui qu'il était avec une compagnie de pauvres, alors il a pleuré de leur pauvreté et marmonna avec ses lèvres. Alors un chevalier s'enquit du cheikh, et il lui donna de l'argent à distribuer aux pauvres.

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– No

↳ By specific individuals

–Yes [specify]: Tous ceux qui appartiennent à l'ordre soufi d'Abu Said al-Baji sont obligés de fréquenter le sanctuaire

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

Notes: تمّ بعد احراق المقام ترميمات كثيرة حافظت عل الهيكل العام للبناء بحسب الفن المعماري التونسي التقليدي كالحجارة المنقوشة والموزاييك والألوان المعروفة في المقامات. كما وقعت إضافات لمكان الضريح وقع اكتشافها كالأعمدة الرومانية والحفصية ممّا أثبت أنّ المقام يعود للقرن 13 وليس 18

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: تهتمّ جهات رسمية بالعناية بالمقام ك الوكالة الوطنية لحماية التراث و المعهد الوطني للتراث و البلدية

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:

– Yes

↳ Priests

– No

↳ Local elites

– Yes

↳ Private contributions

– Yes

Notes: Contributions de la société civile

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: أغلب الحاضرين من سكان سيدي بوسعيد

↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:

–Yes [specify]: يتمّ التجول من المقام تمّ في كامل أرجاء سيدي بوسعيد

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Notes: Les fêtes ou festivals font partie des occasions religieuses, telles que l'Aïd al-Fitr et l'Aïd al-Adha, ou la célébration de l'anniversaire du Prophète "Almaoulid", ou le Nouvel An islamique "Alhijri".

↳ Frequency of festivals

–specify: 1500-2000

↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Elites

– Non-elites

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: يحضر المتساكنون والأجانب و المنتسبين لطريقة سيدي بوسعيد الباجي من المرادين

↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– No

Notes: Les fêtes ou festivals font partie des occasions religieuses, telles que l'Aïd al-Fitr et l'Aïd al-Adha, ou la célébration de l'anniversaire du Prophète "Almaoulid", ou le Nouvel An islamique "Alhijri".

↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:

–number: 500

↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– Yes

↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:

– Elites

– Non-elites

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: الوكالة الوطنية لحماية التراث و المعهد الوطني للتراث

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– Yes

Notes: Le sanctuaire à l'époque du cheikh Abi Saeed avait l'habitude de venir aux pauvres et aux nécessiteux, et il leur fournissait de la nourriture et des cadeaux qui étaient présentés au sanctuaire, en particulier par les riches ou les gouverneurs qui demandaient la bénédiction du cheikh, et le cheikh avait l'habitude de subvenir à leurs besoins matériels en vêtements et en nourriture. Il a également travaillé sur la résolution de problèmes tels que la libération de prisonniers, la libération d'esclaves et de captifs, la guérison de malades et la demande de pluie.

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– No

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: كان الولاية يسترضون الشيخ لطلب مباركتهم وكانوا يقدمون إغانات لكن الشيخ يقدمها للفقراء وفاقدي السند وكان زاهدا في الدنيا

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– I don't know

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